

Evaluation of Photovoltaic Laser Power Converters for Non-Uniform Laser Irradiance Profiles

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Abstract: The non-uniform irradiance of fiber lasers influences the performance of power-by-light systems. We analyze the non-uniformity in both single and triple junction power converters in addition to other parameters that could reduce the efficiency such as manufacturing tolerances or series resistance effect. We present an experimental efficiency of $67.0 \pm 0.9\%$ in triple junction power converters for an input power of 2.8 W using a laser wavelength of 857 nm. We demonstrate thus a high efficiency for non-uniformity irradiance.

1. Introduction

The increasingly popular photovoltaic laser power converters (PVLPCs) for power-by-light (PBL) systems are approaching efficiencies up to almost 70% [1].

Non-uniform irradiance by fiber lasers is an obstacle to approaching so high efficiencies but it is the usual situation in practical systems. Homogenizing the light with ad-hoc optics produces laser power losses. This makes it interesting to analyze the non-uniformity influence on PVLPCs. Can PVLPCs be operated with highly non-uniform irradiances and still achieve high efficiencies?. We present an analysis for GaAs S-PVLPCs (single-junction) and T-PVLPCs (triple-junction). Fill factor (FF) are less degraded in T-PVLPCs due to the lower current handled. However, T-PVLPCs also can be less efficient due to manufacturing tolerances or laser detuning affecting the current matching, and possible tunnel junction breakdown at so high irradiance. We analyze the non-uniformity effect to evaluate the efficiency potential in S-PVLPCs and T-PVLPCs in addition to these other parameters commented. We conclude which one is globally more appropriate for non-uniform irradiance. We also present the experimental results for T-PVLPCs developed at IES-UPM for a non-uniform laser irradiance of 857 nm wavelength, showing efficiencies over 67%.

2. Theoretical model

We obtain I-V curves and calculate their figures of merit using the distributed model developed at IES-UPM [2]. In this model, we define the inverted square front grid geometry of the 3x3 mm PVLPCs, and the characteristics of the non-uniform light expressed as the peak-to-average ratio of laser Gaussian profiles, with values from 1 to 6.

We use the experimental junction parameters obtained in our GaAs PVLPCs and optimize the number of fingers (3 μm width) to maximize the output power for each non-uniformity situation. We also use experimental metal and emitter sheet resistance parameters of 0.03 and 10 Ω/\square , respectively.

3. Results

FF degrades as the input power in the PVLPC increases. S-PVLPCs handle higher currents and have lower

voltages than T-PVLPCs, so the effect of series resistance on the FF becomes more important. Non-uniform irradiance affects the PVLPCs operation even more. The non-uniformity causes the FF to degrade further being more accused in S-PVLPCs. FF degradation due to both non-uniformity and series resistance is globally more severe in S-PVLPCs than in T-PVLPCs (Fig 1).

Fig. 1. Simulated FF of S-PVLPCs (upper panel) and T-PVLPCs (lower panel) as a function of the input power and peak-to-average ratio of the Gaussian laser profile. The front grid is optimized for each peak-to-average ratio at 1 W of input power.

The non-uniformity in the S-PVLPC also affects the efficiency. For an input power of 2.5 W, S-PVLPCs output power drops with the peak-to-average ratio (Fig.2). However, T-PVLPC output power drop is less pronounced at any non-uniform level than S-PVLPC.

Therefore, these results indicate that T-PVLPCs are more efficient than S-PVLPCs for non-uniform irradiance profiles. They can also provide more output voltage necessary to power most equipment. However, T-PVLPCs have some drawbacks such as the potential breakdown of tunnel junctions under high irradiance levels and the sensitivity to laser detuning. Moreover, typical manufacturing tolerances in the semiconductor structure makes the thicknesses of the subcells different from those optimized. This lowers the current generated by the T-PVLPC, affecting the output power and, consequently, the efficiency.

Figure 2 shows the output power against the peak-to-average ratio for a total 2.5 W input power. An output power loss of 40 mW (2.4%) and 110 mW (6.0%) is obtained when applying absorber thickness tolerances of 5 % and 10%, respectively at each non-uniformity level. It means an efficiency loss from 73.1 to 71.4 and 68.7%, respectively, for the case of higher non-uniformity represented as the peak-to-average ratio of 6. These results show that for non-uniform irradiance, T-PVLPC surpasses S-PVLPC efficiency even applying manufacturing tolerances. However, tolerances applied in T-PVLPCs can reduce the efficiency from 74.1 % to 69.6 %, approaching the best value to S-PVLPCs efficiency for uniform irradiance (peak-to-average ratio=1).

Fig. 2. Simulated output power and efficiency of a S-PVLPC (blue line) and T-PVLPC (pink line) as a function of the peak-to-average ratio assuming manufacturing tolerances in the growth thicknesses of 5 % (dark shading) and 10 % (light shading) at 2.5 W of input power.

An optic system can be used to homogenize the laser light and maximize the efficiency. However, the optic losses would affect the overall efficiency of the system. Furthermore, it is also complicated to include optics in most PBL systems so PVLPCs should coexist with non-uniformity irradiance. In this manner, our results suggest that, as compared to S-PVLPCs, T-PVLPCs are a better option for PBL systems because they provide a higher potential efficiency even applying 10 % manufacturing tolerances in the thicknesses grown, and assuming no tunnel junction breakdown.

This analysis has helped us to recently manufacture T-PVLPCs achieving 67.0 ± 0.9 % maximum efficiency at 2.8 W of input power (Fig.3) with the non-uniform illumination of the fiber laser spot. This experimental efficiency supports the theoretical results demonstrating the high-efficiency possibility in T-PVLPCs for non-uniformity irradiance.

Fig. 3. Average efficiency (line) and measurement uncertainty (shading) of T-PVLPC developed and manufactured at IES-UPM for 857 nm non-uniform irradiance laser wavelength.

4. Conclusions

Theoretical results of this work suggest that typical non-uniform irradiance profiles of fiber lasers are devastating for the performance of S-PVLPCs due to series resistance effects on the FF. T-PVLPCs show much lower losses, but are affected by manufacturing tolerances, laser detuning and tunnel-junction breakdown at high intensities. However, we theoretically demonstrate higher efficiencies in T-PVLPCs working with non-uniform irradiances, considering all these effects.

We also demonstrate high experimental efficiency in T-PVLPC. We have achieved a maximum efficiency value of 67.0 ± 0.9 % for an input power of 2.8 W using a non-uniform laser of wavelength 857 nm. We demonstrate that it is possible to achieve high operation efficiencies using T-PVLPCs in PBL systems coexisting with the non-uniform irradiance of fiber lasers.

Acknowledgments

This work is part of the project TEFLON-CM (Y2018/EMT-4892) funded by the Regional Government of Madrid (Comunidad de Madrid) with the support from FEDER Funds (in English, ERDF, European Regional Development Funds). This publication is part of the project EQC2019-005701-P, funded by AEI/10.13039/501100011033, MCIN and ERDF “A way to make Europe”

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